

Studies in Dipolar Aprotic Media : Solvent Effects on the Kinetics of Aromatic Nucleophilic Substitution

S. M. Mayanna and J. R. Raju

The reaction kinetics of the nucleophilic substitution of *p*-nitrochlorobenzene with sodium methoxide have been studied in Dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO)—Methanol mixtures of different compositions. The results show that the rate constant increases with increasing DMSO content and empirical relation is proposed. Arrhenius parameters along with other data are used to discuss the solvation in these mixtures.

Dipolar aprotic solvents like DMSO have recently been receiving increased attention¹. The high dipole moments, dielectric constants and the inability of these solvents to form hydrogen bonds are the factors taken advantage of for a number of anionic reactions. Thus, the reaction between benzyl chloride and sodium methoxide in methanol is accelerated by the addition of DMSO to the solution². The kinetics of the alkaline hydrolysis of several alkyl esters have been studied in water-DMSO mixtures and increase in rate has been observed³. An ester like cedryl acetate which is hard to saponify is hydrolysed in the presence of DMSO⁴. Parker, who studied the rates of several nucleophilic substitution reactions in dipolar aprotic solvents reported that the rate increases by a factor as high as 10^{4.5}. Parker and Miller found that in aromatic nucleophilic substitution, a small quantity of aprotic solvents was necessary for the completion of the reaction. The small quantity of the aprotic solvent presumably solvates the leaving group and facilitates the product formation⁶.

We have studied the reaction of *p*-nitrochlorobenzene with sodium methoxide in mixtures of DMSO and Methanol at various compositions and at different temperatures. This reaction has been studied earlier in pure methanol only⁷. As anticipated the increase in DMSO content of the reaction medium should enhance the rate very much. This effect may be largely due to the inability of the dipolar aprotic solvent to form hydrogen bonds.

EXPERIMENTAL

DMSO (BDH) was distilled over calcium oxide under reduced pressure. Methanol (BDH) was distilled. Both the solvents were stored free from moisture.

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Sodium methoxide solution prepared from freshly out sodium and absolute methanol was standardised with standard hydrochloric acid and used for obtaining DMSO-Methanol mixtures of required composition by volume as follows : a known volume of DMSO was added to a definite volume of the methoxide solution.

Kinetic determinations : Equal volumes of sodium methoxide solution and *p*-chloro-nitrobenzene solution, both of equal molarity, were mixed in a flask cooled in ice. Aliquots, in 5 or 10 ml were, distributed into several drawn out tubes which were then sealed. The tubes were transferred to a thermostat controlled to $\pm 0.1^\circ$. After thermal equilibrium had been reached, a zero reading was obtained for solutions with a DMSO content of 65% by volume and above and not for others.

Analysis : The reaction tube was cooled in ice, broken open and the reaction mixture transferred immediately to standard hydrochloric acid. Unreacted hydrochloric acid was estimated using standard baryta which was protected from carbon dioxide.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Rate constants for the reaction of *p*-nitrochlorobenzene with sodium methoxide in mixtures of DMSO and methanol at various compositions and at different temperatures investigated by us have been calculated, and they were reproducible to within 3%. Arrhenius parameters—frequency factor *A*, and energy of activation E_a have also been determined for three compositions of DMSO-methanol mixtures at different temperatures. All these data are shown in Table 1. However, the reaction beyond 85% DMSO was not studied as it was too fast, and hence not possible to obtain any reproducible kinetics. It is observed from this table that the rate increases enormously with the percentage of DMSO in the medium.

TABLE 1

Kinetics of the Nucleophilic Substitution in DMSO-Methanol Solutions

Vol. percent of DMSO in methanol	Mole fraction** of DMSO in methanol	Temperature in ($^\circ$ C)	$K_1 \times 10^6$ Mole/L $^{-1}$ Sec $^{-1}$	E_a (K. Cal/mole)	Log A (S = ?)
0	0	71.0	8.42	24.050*	11.191 (-9.71 e.u.)
		81.6	23.50		
		100.8	137.00		
50	0.3633	55.9	83.39	23.42	12.4909 (-3.58 e.u.)
		63.7	217.50		
		72.0	435.90		
		75.5	648.30		
65	0.5148	55.0	418.2	21.040	11.6429 (-7.55 e.u.)
		64.0	1052.0		
		72.0	2067.0		
85	0.7639	23.0	287.7	18.820	11.3619 (-9.00 e.u.)
		29.8	601.1		
		35.0	1026.0		
		40.0	1617.0		

* Data from Ref. 7. ** Calculated from percent volume by densities (25 $^\circ$) and molecular weights.

Factors of rate increase in DMSO-methanol mixtures of different compositions at a constant temperature of 50° have also been determined and reported in Table 2. It is observed that as the dipolar aprotic solvent content of the mixture increases, this factor increases enormously.

TABLE 2

Factors of rate increase in DMSO-methanol mixtures of different compositions

Mole fraction of DMSO	Rate constant (105x)* at 50°	Factors with pure methanol as base
0	0.8338	1
0.1965	7.3070	8.764
0.3633	44.7600	5.366 × 10 ¹
0.5148	258.7000	3.103 × 10 ²
0.6316	885.4000	1.062 × 10 ³
0.7639	4187.0000	5.022 × 10 ³

* Rates computed for 50° by Arrhenius parameters (vide table 1).

Kingsbury's explanations⁸ for the increased rates in nucleophilic aromatic substitution reactions in dipolar aprotic-protic solvent mixtures have been subjected to criticism by Parker⁹. Therefore, the increased rates cannot be due to his *conclusions*, that 'catalysis' by DMSO and other related solvents is independent of the charge the nucleophile bears. And also it cannot be due to his suggestion that the mechanism of DMSO catalysis involves polarization of the aromatic substrate by a random DMSO molecule, followed by rapid nucleophilic attack upon this species. Further, a higher-energy species in dipolar aprotic solvents *vs* protic solvents is at variance with the greater solubility of polar organic molecules in the presence of dipolar aprotic solvents and the fact that most organic substrates can be recovered unchanged from solutions containing dipolar aprotic solvents.

Therefore, the enhanced rates in nucleophilic aromatic substitution reactions in dipolar aprotic-protic solvent mixtures may be due to the fact that the DMSO molecules, in, or arranged about the transition state for a reaction in DMSO-methanol mixtures, lower the free energy and hence the energy of activation of the transition state, relative to that for the reaction in pure methanol. This would lead to faster reactions in the mixed solvent mixtures. An interaction of this type is mechanistically quite a different proposition from polarization of the substrate, prior to reaction with the nucleophile. Actually, we have observed a decrease in E_a with the increase in the percentage of DMSO, the dipolar aprotic solvent in the mixture. This readily explains the enormous increase in rate. Lastly, it is likely that the increased rates may also be due to the considerable solvation of the transition state which gives fairly large negative values of entropy of activation with the increased percentage of DMSO.

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Department of Physical Chemistry,
Central College,
Bangalore University.

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